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Educational Potential of Arts

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Abstract:

The article is devoted to the issues of teaching and educating youth by revealing the inner resources of art. It determines the educational potential of art, and describes the ways of its implementation in conditions of education modernization; considers the functional possibilities and prospects for the development of the artistic culture of youth, including in the process of interaction of cultures of different peoples. The author dwells on the components of the national culture, and describes state strategies, attitudes and guidelines in the implementation of the educational potential of art. Much attention is paid in the article to the continuity of traditions, national and artistic values of the Uzbek people, the formation of students' motivation to master the values of national and world artistic culture.

Keywords: art, modernization of education, artistic culture, national culture, world culture, functions of culture, formation of aesthetic needs, aesthetic taste, perception of the world, national originality, national and cultural identity,

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Introduction

Uzbekistan has taken a step into a new decade. Its achievements are becoming history; life is setting it more and more new requirements; great prospects are opening up for even deeper transformations in all spheres of society and the choice of priority areas for modernizing the system of continuous education, which is one of the main sources of training a spiritually and intellectually advanced generation, since it is this generation that will have to transform all spheres of the economy and build the future.

The ability of the education system to meet the needs of individuals and society for high-quality educational services determines the level and prospects of the country's economic and spiritual development. The concept of modernization of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan implies innovative changes in an integral pedagogical system, as well as the creation of favourable conditions for the personal development of the younger generation in accordance with the requirements of modern society. Uzbekistan is actualizing the need for the optimal use of such an educational resource as art, which is the most important means of formation and development of spiritual, moral and aesthetic ideals of individuals in conditions of mass culture.

One of the indicators of spiritual and intellectual development of youth is their creative potential. The core and spiritual potential of creative development of individuals is artistic culture and its most important components – art, material and artistic activity, and sciences that study artistic culture. It is a mobile and dynamic system that as a process functions in society in stages: a) creation of artistic values; b) their distribution by various channels; and c) their assimilation. Artistic culture is of particular value in conditions of reconstruction of socioeconomic relations. The process of forming the artistic culture of youth will be more effective if a complex impact of all types of art is carried out on its emotional and volitional sphere [1]. The principle of “integrating the arts” by V.Volynkin is put forward as one of the leaders in solving the problem of children’s artistic development: “the complex of arts acts holistically and systemically, forming by its own a new and higher level aesthetic perception” and is necessary for more than 30 adequate perceptions and understanding of the author’s intention by children [2:357].

Main part

It is known that art education and upbringing are important components of stimulating the creative abilities of individuals, based on the development of interest in human cultural artistic traditions and assimilation of world and domestic creative heritage. The study of artistic culture, in particular, the national characteristics of professional fine arts in the country, must be considered as an effective means of educating the younger generation in the spirit of internationalism, as well as respect for the customs and artistic traditions of various peoples and nationalities. Mastering successfully the objects of national and world artistic heritage contributes to the formation of creative thinking of individuals, the emotional and aesthetic assimilation of the phenomena of reality and the development of own creative abilities, which ensure the practical reproduction in independent creativity of the national colour, original artistic images, and most importantly, the formation of moral and aesthetic qualities of the younger generation.

Artistic culture performs a number of functions:

- Aesthetic – formation of a sense of beautiful and aesthetic taste, aesthetic consciousness;
- Ideological – assessing author’s ideological position, his perception of the world;
- Cognitive – contributing to the discovery of historical facts and author’s psychology for oneself, and knowledge of the subtleties of his perception of the world;
- Communicative – art as a conductor of knowledge and feelings, a means of spiritual communication;
- Educational – ensuring the formation of a spiritual and integral personality, and human values, comprehension of humanistic categories of goodness, beauty, etc.

From early childhood, anyone comes into contact with works of art. Thus, the mother puts her love into the lullaby satisfying the child’s need for safety. According to the researchers, lullabies greatly contribute to the development of the spirituality of the individual, and form a positive personal potential. Lullabies harmoniously combine the elements of oral folk art and the spiritual world of the mother.

Starting from early school age, pupils should become familiar with the most important layer of artistic culture – folk art: folk crafts, folklore, folk traditions, customs, early and modern traditional art (architecture, miniature painting, calligraphy, alabaster carving, stone carving, wood carving and etc.)

An inclination for artistic and aesthetic perception of the world is inherent in the very nature of man. So, the instinct of children’s creativity is manifested in their perception of the world through the prism of imagery and imagination. In this regard, V.Sukhomlinsky noted the following: “Children should live in the world of beauty, games, fairy tales, music, drawings, creativity”. It is important that the child sees the beauty, stops in front of it in amazement, makes the beauty a part of his spiritual life, and is delighted with the beauty of words and images [3:18].

Thanks to its visual-graphic form, fine art is close and understandable to children; it is human in the deepest sense of this word. Examples of moral behaviour embodied in artistic images introduce children to the laws of human communication in the best way, make them treat someone else’s pain with understanding and compassion, sincerely empathize with someone else’s joy, and be sensitive to those who are near. Fine art “creates a person and is addressed to a person, knocks at his heart, serves to unity and involvement in human relationships, indicates the direction of a moral deed” [4:48].

In order to protect our youth from the “general culture”, first of all, it is necessary to cultivate a healthy artistic and aesthetic taste. The educational function of art requires the improvement of all its branches. Today, the main attention is paid to the development of aesthetic culture of individuals in the field of education, press, media, Internet, information and communication technologies and other means of culture, such as theater, cinema, literature, music, fine and applied arts, which have a direct impact on the consciousness of youth.

The issues of developing the sphere of culture and arts has been one of the priority directions of the state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for many years. In 2017, a program of comprehensive measures was approved based on international experience to improve the

cultural and spiritual level of youth by attracting them to art and familiarizing them with the best examples of national and world culture. Among them are: holding reviews and festivals of theatrical art that reveal the images of contemporaries and heroes of our time; holding creative meetings and master classes with foreign musicians and composers; wide propaganda about the rich culture of Uzbekistan in the international arena, etc. [5]

Naturally, all forms of art, developing and improving, serve the main goal – the spiritual education of youth. The state constantly shows concern for the development of art and is the main support in the further modernization of society and upbringing of creative youth, who are tolerant of the cultures of the peoples of world civilization.

In recent years, all the main components of the national culture have received dynamic development and support: historical and cultural heritage, artistic creativity on a professional and non-professional (amateur) basis, authentic folklore groups, club activities, library and museum work, cinematography, folk arts and crafts.

At the same time, work experience of in the higher education system indicates that as a result of a thoughtful and systematic introduction of youth to the heritage of domestic and world artistic culture, familiarization with the creative heritage of Uzbek and foreign artists during conversations, disputes, electives, creative evenings, excursions and practical lessons of fine arts, the following general conclusions can be made:

- Artistic culture as a whole solves the most important task of propaganda, familiarizing wide circles of the younger generation with national cultural values, forming and strengthening the aesthetic self-awareness of youth;
- Local features of the original professional fine arts, which reflect the current problems of society and the most important stages in people's history, are inextricably linked with the development of characteristic trends in world culture.

In disciplines of an artistic and aesthetic cycle in higher educational institutions, it is advisable to use the didactic principles known in pedagogy that qualitatively affect the growth dynamics of students' artistic and creative abilities: the principle of a holistic view of the world (formation of a single picture of the world based on establishing a connection between various educational areas and comparing the information received with their life experience, creation of an active transformative world perception, adoption of an integrative interaction approach to solving educational problems in lessons); the principle of variability (choice of an individual trajectory of development, hypothesis of the optimal variant); the principle of continuity (continuity in all levels of education at the level of methodology, content and methods); the principle of psychological comfort (removing stress-forming factors in the educational process, creating an atmosphere of psychological comfort (a situation of success) and emotional richness in lessons); the principle of creativity (maximum orientation towards creativity in educational activities, use of interactive teaching methods aimed at creating problem situations in lessons and stimulating students' creative self-expression), the perception of literary and graphic material in the context of social macro- and micro situations, understanding the "dialectics" of the soul [6:36]. In addition, it is advisable to use a number of educational and innovative technologies that ensure the implementation of the following conditions: high professional skills of the teacher-artist; creation of problem-search situations and creative tasks aimed at the development of

aesthetic characteristics of individuals and artistic and pedagogical skills of students; creation of a creative atmosphere in the process of research and artistic and creative activities; optimal motivation of students to form worldview positions and value orientations.

A particularly effective means of moral and ethical formation of an individual in the process of art education is a systematic familiarization of the younger generation with the creative heritage of outstanding artists and masters of applied arts of the country. This makes it possible not only to directly perceive the originals of highly professional works of artists, which form the consciousness of the mediated involvement of young students in the world of high art, but also contributes to the formation of skills in creative analysis of portrait images of compatriots, historical plots, recognizable pictures of nature, original subject compositions in works of fine art, as well as traditional and modern works of decorative and applied art, ancient architectural monuments and other objects of artistic culture, which stimulates the development of creativity and the creative potential of youth. [2]

At the same time, additional measures are being taken to create an effective system for working with gifted youth, support their initiatives aimed at realizing the talent and potential of the younger generation, as well as provide training for highly-demanded specialists capable of adequately representing the interests of the country in the international arena at a high professional level.

In this regard, today great importance is being attached in the country to the issues of increasing attention to youth and their wide involvement in culture, art and sports, forming skills in the use of information technologies, and promoting reading books among the younger generation. Especially, in recent years, a lot of work has been carried out to develop creativity, creative potential, abilities and talent of youth. In particular, 5 initiatives that were put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, aimed at creating specific conditions for the upbringing and education of modern youth, can be cited as an example. In the first initiative of the President, it was proposed to increase the interest of young people in music, art, literature, theater and other forms of art [7].

For each initiative, a project program of measures was developed, the implementation of which was planned in 2019-2020. The project program on the first initiative envisages attracting 2 million young people from 14 to 30 years old to culture and art. It was planned to open additional classes in children's music and art schools, and in cultural centers – clubs for instrumental, vocal performance and fine arts, "youth clubs", theater-studios, and children's ensembles. A positive experience of famous artists, creative workers and masters of folk crafts of decorative and applied arts in mentoring and training youth is being introduced.

In order to raise to a qualitatively new level the work on the identification, selection, training and education of gifted youth, further support and encouragement of young talents, agencies have been established for the functioning of presidential, creative and specialized schools with progressive forms of education, pedagogical technologies and information innovations, equipped with modern libraries with works of national and world literature, music, cinema, sculpture, applied arts and other creative areas. These are the creative schools named after Abdulla Oripov, Hamid Olimjon and Zulfiya, Muhammad Yusuf, Ibroyim Yusupov, Erkin Vohidov, Muhammad Rizo Erniyozbek ogli Agahi, Halima Khudoiberdieva and Abdulla Kadiri.

Also, a number of large projects are being implemented in order to revive, study and use the rich cultural heritage of the people in the education of youth. In particular, the Center of Islamic Culture of Uzbekistan is being created in the capital, and the Imam Bukhari International Research Center is being established in Samarkand. The activities of the Center for the Study of the Cultural Wealth of Uzbekistan Abroad and the Center for the New History of Uzbekistan are being organized. A lot of work is being done to improve the culture of reading, improve the spheres of culture and art, and organize creative schools and centers in the regions, which will be named after great figures of literature and art.

Thus, the ongoing reforms and measures taken to modernize the education system are currently aimed at the comprehensive education and development of modern youth.

The abovementioned allowed us to formulate appropriate attitudes and guidelines in realizing the educational potential of art as a means of:

- strengthening ties between ethnic groups and states, a way of mutual understanding, interaction and mutual enrichment of national cultures; familiarizing youth with the cultural values of the world;

- a dialogue of cultures between generations of different ethnic groups; creation of a favourable socio-cultural space in order to expand cultural and humanitarian cooperation, and realize the ideas of peace and democracy [1];

- building up spiritual and moral values and orientations of individuals in the process of cognition of works of art;

- implementation of informational, cognitive, creative, purifying (catharsis), relaxing and spiritual potential of art in the educational process; stimulating students to self-education and creative self-realization; mobilization of potential cognitive resources of individuals;

- development of cultural cooperation in the field of education; enrichment of the content of education with general and ethno-cultural knowledge; use of innovations in teaching, modern technologies for the formation of the artistic culture of youth; productive analysis of the general and special in the culture of different nations (language, everyday life, folklore, works of art);

- forming the national-artistic culture of youth in the process of formation of its civil, patriotic and aesthetic consciousness;

- forming the interest and needs of youth in the independent mastery of layers of artistic culture, creative activity for the creation, study and promotion of works of art;

- assistance to youth in the preservation of monuments of national and world culture embodying the historical memory and cultural heritage of the past;

- formation of persistent cultural and ideological immunity among youth, a critical attitude towards pseudo-cultural and ideologically alien models and stereotypes of general culture (subculture).

Thus, art-based aesthetics and their relationships are one of the foundations of spiritual education that forms the need for the perception of beauty, which is an important basis for the aesthetically rich worldview of modern youth. Realization of the educational potential of art contributes to the growth of national self-awareness, the preservation of the spiritual cultural heritage of peoples and the formation of a whole aesthetic image of youth, behind whom is the future of the country.

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